

Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe

Ways to Decrease TCO and Infrastructure Related Costs

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Abstract

An analysis of Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) is widely used to support acquisition and planning decisions for a wide range of assets that bring significant maintenance or operating costs across ownership life. This calculation of TCO aggregates the initial investment as capital expenditure (CapEx) with the operational expenditure (OpEx) along the whole life cycle of the asset. It is a central concern e.g. in budgeting and asset life cycle management, when prioritizing acquisition proposals. Not surprisingly, evaluating the TCO of a supercomputing system is a widely used approach to compare different options.

Any data centre, especially an HPC centre, requires an advanced infrastructure which supports the efficient work with computing and data resources. Although depending on the particular customer situation, infrastructure related costs are important contributors to the TCO, energy being among those costs, one of the most important cost driving factors to be considered in a TCO calculation. The worldwide fastest supercomputers of 2017 consume up to 18 MW, close to what is generally considered as the upper limit for the electricity budget (20 MW). Our study shows that on average the CapEx for IT equipment represents less than half of the total costs (46.8 %) and a large fraction of costs (33.8 %) is due to the investment incurred in developing the infrastructure and the related operational costs collectively. A share of 11.1 % of the TCO is attributed to personnel costs.

Reducing TCO is generally challenging and there are no simple recipes. The decrease of costs has to be analysed in conjunction with strategic goals of the data centres, defined requirements and SLAs. Therefore, it's a multi-layered analysis and not only a simple decrease of costs. Changes that help to reduce costs in one part of the system may result in an increase of costs in other parts. So there is a need for trade-off analysis taking all system and data infrastructure related costs into account. This also requires to make certain assumptions about the usage of the system, and the typical workload it will operate and to balance Time-to-Solution (TtS) and Energy-to-Solution (EtS) to target the "best value for money".

This white paper is based on a questionnaire that has been sent out to PRACE partners in work package "HPC Commissioning and Prototyping" (WP5) to find the most relevant cost factors which have to be considered when purchasing, installing or upgrading, and operating a state-of-the-art HPC centre. Another goal of this report is to assess the increasing role of the infrastructure and the great power consumption, especially with regards to the upcoming exascale systems. Promising strategies for cutting costs while preserving high-performance are discussed and examples of best-practices are listed. Finally, a practical example is given to what extent the TCO concept is used in HPC procurements at PRACE partner sites.

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Introduction

Those who purchase or manage IT systems have a high interest in Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) and especially in infrastructure related costs as it turns out that there is a large difference between IT systems purchase prices and systems costs. Total cost of ownership does not only comprise purchase costs but attempts to uncover all costs of ownership across the full life cycle of the acquisition [1]. Tools have been developed for modelling TCO to understand all the components of data centre costs, including both capital and operational expenses [2].

Public research high-performance computing (HPC) data centres which are at the forefront of performance requirements differ from enterprise data centres as they are often the first to experience the disruptive changes in technology and requirements [3]. Infrastructure related costs and energy cost are among the most important cost driving factors to be considered in a TCO calculation, which highly depend on the particular customer situation.

This paper investigates the most relevant cost factors which must be considered when purchasing, installing or upgrading, and operating an HPC system and is intended to draw attention to the increasing importance of the infrastructure in view of the upcoming exascale systems and their strongly growing electricity consumption. Furthermore, it may also help to develop strategies for cost reductions without diminishing the return on investment (ROI). Dealing with ROI, i.e. the assessment of outcomes of HPC, is extremely difficult as it is unlike business ROI not financial but measured as intellectual ROI, e.g. publications or graduations. Eventually, another goal pursued by this paper is providing best practices for using a TCO analysis in the procurement of HPC systems. Here, the strategy aims at getting the best computing capacity for a given TCO or, alternatively, getting a defined computing capacity for the lowest overall budget. As the computing capacity is very closely linked with the data centre environment we consider the TCO with all other aspects which are necessary to run the required HPC system.

In Section 1 the relevant cost categories for a TCO analysis are listed and measuring methods are discussed how to determine their relative amount. Section 2 presents a number of strategies for saving infrastructural, operational, and other TCO related costs. Section 3 provides a survey of state-of-the-art costs identified at a set of European centres and highlights a few best-practice examples for successfully implementing cost saving strategies. In section 4 a TCO-assisted procurement-method of supercomputers is discussed. Section 5 concludes the white paper.

This white paper was prepared as part of the work conducted under PRACE-5IP/WP5, building on previous work performed by PRACE-4IP/WP5.

1. TCO cost categories

A TCO analysis for HPC requires the identification of all the spending that can be expected during the ownership period. Cost categories can be broken down into investment and procurement expenses that do not depend on the lifetime of a system and operational costs incurring over the whole life cycle of the system. Other costs like insurance or financing costs play a minor role.

1.1 Investment and procurement expenditure (CapEx)

A basic part of an HPC system's TCO estimate consists of the IT hardware equipment and deployment costs. This comprises the supercomputer itself, including system setup and disposal costs, as well as related IT equipment like the storage system and computer centre network. In addition, evolutions and upgrades within the years of operation should be considered.

In an HPC environment, scientific applications run by the users from scientific communities are extremely important. So when regarding costs, adaptation and porting of the application codes to a new compute architecture has to be taken into account as well as the initial training effort to help users write efficient and scalable code and tune their jobs to exploit the essential characteristics of the new system.

When installing a new supercomputer, the building and technical facility housing the HPC centre might require a substantial enhancement of the existing infrastructure. This may affect reinforcement of the building's structural stability, floor space for IT equipment and technical facilities as well as the provisions for power supply, e.g. transformers, UPS, distribution, and cooling, e.g. pipes, pumps, chillers, heat exchangers. Investment in security and monitoring, e.g. fire protection, leakage detection, resource consumption measurement is also requisite.

Preliminary procurement expenses, e.g. due to determining user and infrastructure requirements and finally selecting the system, as well as administrative costs for the tendering procedure and the order also have an impact on TCO and should not be neglected.

1.2 Operational expenditure (OpEx)

When regarding costs in daily operation, maintenance of the supercomputer and the related IT equipment, including vendor support, must be taken into account as well as expenses for software licenses (unless already included in the purchase price CapEx). The permanent task of user training and support has also to be reflected here.

The maintenance of building and technical facilities must also be considered as a relevant cost factor. In recent years the dominating fraction of operational costs are cost of power consumption of the IT equipment. The other major costs are power consumption for the IT cooling and power consumption caused by the losses introduced in power transfers in the infrastructure.

To ensure a reliable normal course operation, security and monitoring systems, e.g. fire protection, leakage detection, resource consumption measurement, have to be provided and paid for.

2. Strategy for reducing costs

Regarding strategies to reduce TCO of HPC systems many trade-offs have to be weighted. Depending on the local situation different options related to system density have to be assessed.

From the infrastructure point of view, on the one hand, building a sustainable infrastructure ready for re-use at follow-up installations is a key value. On the other hand, right-sizing the power and cooling installation to the precise energy requirements may avoid investments in equipment that will never be used. Both can be achieved if the infrastructure is designed in a modular way.

A major challenge for enabling exascale systems are energy costs, which will likely dominate TCO for such systems. Therefore, reducing TCO by means of making computing systems and data centre infrastructures significantly more energy efficient will be crucial. Dynamic tuning of hardware parameters may also be an option to reduce energy costs.

Improving productivity and system availability by reducing mean-time-to-repair based on refined monitoring for fast fault localization and fault prediction combined with preventive hardware replacement will contribute to increasing the return on investment.

2.1 Optimise system density according to infrastructure settings

The selection of a new supercomputer is partly affected by the local infrastructure settings and its deployment has to be optimised within a given range of options.

HPC sites report significantly higher loads (both static weight and power load) for compute cabinets as well for networking and data storage cabinets. Latency and bandwidth sensitivity drives the need for shorter cables and thus more tightly packed systems as well as the need to pack ever greater compute capacity into a given footprint, energy and cooling envelope [3]. For highly scalable systems cable lengths are extremely important and the limitations of copper as well as its cost lead to the willingness to keep cables short as much as possible.

So regarding floor space, high-density systems help to get the most out of the available infrastructure settings when installing an HPC supercomputer. As a trade-off, dense systems come with a higher weight per m² entailing in most cases the necessity of an enforcement of the raised floor or the cement floor at considerable costs, unless the infrastructure is already designed to handle such loads, e.g. if the centre was recently built.

Dense systems come also with a higher power load per cabinet and require specific cooling options to remove the heat. Sites having before solely housed air cooled systems in their computer room are faced with the trade-off of either investing in a new liquid cooling infrastructure or staying with air cooling solutions at the expense of much higher operating costs later on.

The available or preferable cooling options depend on the density of the system, the current infrastructure settings on site and the geographic position of the site. Pros and cons of solutions, e.g. high/low-temperature liquid cooling, hybrid cooling, air cooling within certain density limits, are discussed later in this chapter.

A retrofit of an existing building requires careful considerations of trade-offs and costs regarding energy efficiency, e.g. of air-cooling and liquid (free) cooling preconditions to accommodate the equipment. The design of a new data centre building demands quite a number of strategic decisions. It is advisable to break infrastructure down into modules that can be added when needed and include pre-built connection points for the addition of infrastructure modules. Some decisions have to be decided at the beginning, e.g. place cabinets on raised floor or slab on grade, and can hardly be changed in retrospect. In some cases, a container approach may be cheaper than a major retrofit of an old HPC centre.

2.2 Build sustainable data infrastructure

Current data centre infrastructures are built for maximum design power consumption. Since data centres are traditionally planned with a lifetime of 15-30 years in mind the data centre infrastructure has to be planned ahead to facilitate re-using of components. Key parts of the infrastructure are typically updated several times during its lifetime and electrical devices should be state-of-the-art and operated at a high level of utilization. Over-provision may lead to a less efficient operational mode as during the early lifetime of the data centre the power consumption of the installed IT systems will not get close to the maximum design power. One way to reduce operating costs would be what Google calls “Energy-Proportional Computing”. The idea is that the infrastructure can grow with the IT demand reducing the capacity overhead and, therefore, allowing the data centre infrastructure to stay in a more energy efficient operating point. One way to approach this challenge would be a modular data centre design. Here, data centre infrastructure components can be added with growing IT needs. A drawback to this approach is that, currently, in public procurements (like most PRACE data centres are built) money is guaranteed only for the original building phase but there is no guarantee for the availability of funds for future upgrades.

Another issue that requires some over-provisioning is that while the normal average operating power consumption will be closer to 50-75% of the peak power consumption, the infrastructure has to be designed to handle the peak consumption. For example, the SuperMUC Phase1 system at Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) [4] has a Linpack power consumption of 2.7 MW but in normal operation the power consumption averages around 2.2 MW.

Figure 1: SuperMUC power consumption (2/2013)

One of the earlier power measurements on SuperMUC Phase1 shows the power variability clearly (Figure 1). Here the IT power consumption varies between 500 kW and 2 MW. The cooling infrastructure consumption is also slightly variable leading to an overall power consumption between 750 kW and 2.5 MW with a 2.8 MW peak.

Another challenge for sustainable data centre infrastructure is the increased use of direct and indirect liquid cooling in the top of the line HPC systems. Currently, the connection from building infrastructure to the IT system is tightly coupled with the IT system integrator. This means that even though the IT system-cooling infrastructure requires a substantial amount of investment it might not be usable for the next HPC system. One approach for HPC data centres would be working together on installation standards, which would help to allow the re-use of IT room cooling infrastructure over multiple generations of HPC systems.

2.3 Optimise cooling costs

2.3.1 Traditional cooling

The traditional way of cooling computer halls is by using Computer Room Air Conditioning (CRAC) units with a compressor and direct expansion of a gas together with an outdoor condenser unit. This has been used for computer halls with low density as well as for HPC with lower densities for a long time. As a rule of thumb around 1/3 of computing power is used for the compressors and fans of the cooling. Thus this is not the most cost efficient method of cooling but the installation is simple and the equipment required is produced in large quantities so the investment and installation costs are low.

2.3.2 Modern HPC cooling costs

Numerous methods to get better efficiency exist today. We can distinguish between air-cooled and liquid cooled computers. A high temperature of the output is important to get rid of the heat or to be able to use the heat for the purpose of heating buildings in colder climates. In order to get a good temperature on the output it is important to capture the heat as close to the source (the electronics) as possible. Another way of getting efficient cooling is right-sizing the cooling infrastructure. This can be in form of module based cooling where you can add modules when the need increases or pumps and fans that can be continually adjusted.

2.3.2.1 Liquid cooling

High-end computing systems in the future will have considerably higher density than today in order to reduce the power consumption (communication over long distances increases the power consumption) and the data transfer time. This will require some form of liquid cooling. When the liquid is led to the processors and other electronics in pipes of copper, other metals or plastics this is called direct liquid cooling. The output temperature from the direct liquid cooling is close to the surface temperature of the electronics which can give an output temperature in the range of 45-55 °C. This means that heat can be dissipated outdoors without any compressors etc. The liquid can be water or some special fluid. With special fluids, a phase change (boiling) can occur at the hot electronics. In this case, the heat of the special liquid is exchanged with normal water close to the computer. The fluid in its gaseous form can evaporate to the heat exchanger directly or can be lead to the heat exchanger by a heat pipe. All direct liquid cooling is highly efficient and often add just 5-10 % in pump power to the computing power.

2.3.2.2 Immersion cooling

A special form of direct liquid cooling is the immersion cooling where the entire board or even the entire computer is submerged in some non-conductive fluid either in an open or closed container. Immersion cooling can be one phase or two phases. Immersion cooling is as efficient as the other forms of direct liquid cooling but may have a lower investment cost since it, in many cases, doesn't require so much special equipment (no pipes, no special board etc.). In cases where each electronic board is placed in a specially designed container, the investment cost can go up due to the special design and currently low productions volumes. The space used can be larger in the case where open containers are used as these containers are less high but wider and thus require extra space. Immersion cooling also often adds extra complexity to the maintenance of the computer (liquid draining, cleaning from oil etc.) and optical cabling can also pose a problem.

2.3.2.3 Hybrid cooling

In hybrid cooling, the electronics are cooled by air and the air is cooled by a heat exchanger in the same rack. The heat exchanger can be a cooled door or a more integrated design (as for example the Cray XC40). The hybrid cooling is in between the efficiency of a good air-cooling and a direct liquid cooling. The air needs fans to be moved around (but much less than in traditional air cooling with CRAC units) and you also have the pumps from the liquid that consume power. The output temperature is also lower than direct liquid cooling (typically 15 - 30 °C). This makes it harder to get rid of the heat or to use it for heat-re-use.

2.3.3 Air cooling

As mentioned above high-end systems in the future will be liquid cooled. Air-cooling may still be required to remove the heat that does not go into the liquid of hybrid-cooled systems. For smaller installations where the highest densities of computing and hence power density are not absolutely required some form of air-cooling may still be a viable option also in the future.

However, if a new computer hall is built or and an old one is refurbished it is a strong recommendation to include a water loop which can be operated at different selectable temperatures (no industry standard for temperatures exists today) or have several loops at different temperatures.

2.3.3.1 Direct expansion

There are many solutions for air-cooling. Computer Room Air Conditioners with direct expansion were mentioned as a reference above as the traditional way of cooling. CRAC units with compressors where the heat directly goes to liquid are basically of the same efficiency as using direct expansion with the benefit that the units are more flexible but also being slightly more costly.

2.3.3.2 System without compressor

If the temperatures are in the correct range a system without a compressor can be used. This, however, requires that the outdoor temperature or the temperature for alternative cooling sources is considerably lower than the output water and hence the warm air from the computers.

2.3.3.3 Optimisations

According to the principals for air cooling the heat should be caught as close to the source as possible and hot air and cooled air should be mixed as little as possible. This is to keep the temperature up which makes the transition to liquid easier and with less cooling coil area used. Another important way to increase the temperature is to increase the ambient temperature in the computer hall. Modern computers can easily operate in temperatures over 30 °C, however, the temperature is often set to 22 – 24 °C because of tradition or comfort reasons.

The first step to separate the cool and hot air is to introduce hot and cold aisles. This should always be implemented today. The next step for a more efficient cooling is to introduce some form of enclosure so that the hot and cooled air go different ways and are separated by airtight enclosures. This is closer to the hybrid air – liquid cooling mentioned above in efficiency and temperatures.

2.3.3.4 Direct Air Cooling

In areas with reasonable cold climates, we can use direct air-cooling, which is when you let the outdoor air cool the computer hall directly or via some kind of mechanical heat exchange system. The only thing that is required is a large fan that takes in the air in one end of the computer hall and let the air out in the other end. Normally the air is filtered to avoid particles from air pollution. The efficiency can be really high but may pose problems with particles, pollution and air humidity. Using a mechanical heat exchange system eliminates most of the problems but also reduces the efficiency of the solution.

2.3.4 Novel cooling sources

Other novel approaches are to use cold water from nearby lake or sea. Ground water from the bedrock can also be used. In some areas, district cooling is implemented. This can be highly environmentally friendly with the fees lower than the cost to produce your own cooling but still substantial.

2.3.5 Heat re-use

The heat from the computers can be used for heating of buildings. For the temperatures of direct liquid cooling and with an appropriately designed heating system the heat can be used directly without increasing the temperatures. But in most cases, some kind of compressor is needed. In many cases, with heat re-use, a large fraction of the energy cost can be recovered but this is highly depending on the local conditions. Heat re-use is used quite frequently today and starts to be a proven technology. In areas with district cooling or heating, the heat can sometimes be sold to the district heating/cooling company. In areas with a lower need for heat, the heat can be transferred to cooling with adsorption coolers which is a novel technology.

Heat Re-use using adsorption cooling has been practised at LRZ for quite some time. For large HPC systems any cooling overhead will have a measurable financial impact. Figure 2 shows the Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the chiller-supported and chiller-less cooling infrastructure at LRZ (January till June 2016). The COP shows how much electrical power is needed to generate a specific amount of cold. A COP of 10 means that for 10W of cooling power 1W of electricity is needed. At LRZ the chiller-supported cold water cooling infrastructure has a COP between 4 and 10, whereas the COP of the chiller-less infrastructure is between 10 and 25. Therefore the use of mechanical chillers for cold-water production needs to be eliminated.

One possible way is the use of adsorption chillers, which produce cold using heat. In HPC the waste heat of the compute system can be exploited. This implies the use of direct liquid cooling which is also the main requirement for other IT waste heat re-use options such as building heat in northern Europe.

Figure 2: COP of chiller-less and chiller supported cooling infrastructure at LRZ

Adsorption cooling uses the process of solid matter adsorption to generate cold energy via water evaporation. First results show that this technology is promising [5] but that it also has some challenges [6].

The first challenge arises from the fact that current adsorption chillers are more efficient with higher driving water temperatures while higher water temperatures have adverse effects on the IT power consumption and on the amount of consumed IT power that can be captured in the direct cooling loop. Figure 3 shows the power increase of one chassis of the CoolMUC2 system at LRZ (Intel Xeon E5-2690 v3 ("Haswell")).

HT-DLC Inlet Temperature (°C)	El. Power (W)	Increase (%)	Temp (°C)
30	4815	-	50.14
35	4844	0.6	55.35
40	4877	1.3	60.15
45	4901	1.8	65.25
50	4915	2.1	67.31

Figure 3: Power consumption of one CoolMUC2 chassis at different water cooling temperatures

As can be seen, the power consumption increases by 2.1% at 50°C cooling water inlet temperature compared to 30°C. If one doesn't re-use heat, the take away message from the above figures is to run HPC systems as cold as possible without the use of mechanical chillers.

The second challenge for the use of adsorption chillers is the decrease of the IT power captured in the direct liquid cooling loop with increased water temperatures. Figure 4 shows the heat captured (total bar) and the useful energy for the adsorption chiller (orange bar). At low temperatures (40°C) about 80% of the CoolMUC2 power consumption is captured in the direct liquid cooling loop but only 45% of that heat is usable by the adsorption chiller. With higher temperatures, the captured heat decreases but the usefulness increases. At 55°C less than 60% of the IT power consumption is captured in the liquid cooling loop but all of it can be used by the adsorption chiller.

Figure 4: IT power consumption captured in the direct liquid cooling loop of the CoolMUC2 system

Taking those two effects into account, Sankey diagrams for different operation scenarios can be used to analyse the setup efficiency (more details in [7]).

Figure 5 shows the energy flows at the operation point of the traditional setup (CoolMUC2 is chiller-less cooled and the 12 storage racks of SuperMUC Phase2 are cooled via rear door heat exchangers using chiller-supported cold water). The average data for 11 months (Jan 2016 till Nov 2016) was used for this analysis. The CoolMUC2 consumed 117.53 kW from which 102.72 kW is cooled using the chiller-less cooling infrastructure. Using the COP of this infrastructure over the 11 months the chiller-less cooling loop required 5.93 kW to remove that heat. 14.81 kW is removed via the central room air conditioning (CRAC) units requiring 3.33 kW of electrical power. The SuperMUC Phase2 storage racks required 45.60 kW of cold which was produced via the cold water (mechanical chiller-supported) cooling infrastructure consuming 11.27 kW of electrical power. The whole setup has a COP of 7.95.

Figure 5: Sankey diagram of CollMUC2 setup with traditional cooling at inlet temperature of 30°C

Figure 6 shows the energy flows for the adsorption chiller setup. Here the CoolMUC2 consumes an additional 1.8% of power (45°C inlet vs. 30°C). From the total power consumption 86.33 kW is captured in the direct liquid cooling loop driving the adsorption chiller. The other 33.63 kW have to be removed by the CRAC units consuming 7.49 kW of electrical power. The adsorption chiller uses 7.17 kW of electrical power to remove the CoolMUC2 heat and to produce the 45.60 kW of cold water needed by the SuperMUC Phase2 storage racks. The overall system COP for this setup is 11.27.

Figure 6: Sankey diagram of CoolMUC2 with adsorption chiller setup at inlet temperature of 45°C

From this analysis it is clear that one of the major efficiency challenges for the adsorption chiller is the increased heat that needs to be removed by the CRAC units with increased water inlet temperatures. A fictive calculation for reducing the heat radiation into the air to 5% shows a COP of 16.52 which is as good as the chiller-less infrastructure COP at LRZ. This means that producing cold water via adsorption chillers is as cheap as chiller-less cooling if this obstacle can be overcome.

2.4 Optimise infrastructure power costs

The cost of electrical power of an HPC data centre results from the combination of the energy consumption (usually expressed in kWh) and the electricity price – the price for a given power consumption of electricity (usually expressed in €/kWh – even if the formula is more complex).

Regarding the power consumption, several strategies described in other sections of this chapter aim at reducing the overall power consumption of an HPC data centre by reducing the power consumption of the cooling system (see section 2.3) or the power consumption of the IT equipment (see section 2.6).

2.4.1 Reduce losses in the power distribution of an HPC centre

A typical organization of the power distribution is presented in Figure 7:

Figure 7: Data centre power distribution organisation

The goal is to reduce the losses due to the transportation of electricity, power conversion, auxiliary systems (like light) in order to use a higher possible fraction of the electricity from the utility to power the IT equipment (CPU, memory, drives, etc.). This can be reached by a combination of the following measures:

Choice of an architecture optimised according to the requirements, both in terms of system availability and according to the local electrical grid behaviour.

- Depending on the quality of the local grid, a common practice is to use UPS for a limited fraction of the IT equipment (possibly in combination with the usage of ultra-capacitors in the IT equipment) in order to avoid the losses due to UPS. Another way is to use UPS systems with some kind of “energy saving” mode which is used in normal operation but when a power problem occurs can switch over to double-conversion really fast.
- Limiting the length of LV power cables and possibly using bus bars to reduce losses in the wires is also a common practice.

Selecting components with high efficiency in the range of power they are expected to operate. For example:

- UPS powering critical IT equipment usually operate at 50% load; they should be selected in order to have a good efficiency for such load.

- Light in the computer room should switch off automatically when not needed and be based on efficient components (like LED).
- High-efficiency PSU can provide a better efficiency (up to a few %) than conventional PSU.

More details can be found in two previous white papers published in the context of the PRACE-IIP project:

- Electricity in HPC Centres, Marcin Pospieszny (PSNC)
- Redundancy and Reliability for an HPC Data Centre, Erhan Yilmaz (UHEM), Ladina Gilly (CSCS)

2.4.2 Get best electricity price

Regarding the electricity, getting the best price involves a discussion with the utility and making sure that each party understands the needs and constraints of the other. Another way is to start a tender of purchasing at the best energy price, e.g. by participating in a tender of local public organisations, like universities, local administration, governmental organisations etc.

The strategy may differ quite a lot between countries since the local context is usually different. However, several strategies may apply:

- Shedding load during peak demand
- Shifting load during peak demand
- Variable pricing

More details can be found in several very interesting papers produced in the context of the EEHPCWG (The Energy Efficient HPC Working Group), see e.g. [8]: “Supercomputing Centers and Electricity Service Providers: A Geographically Distributed Perspective on Demand Management in Europe and the United States”, Proceedings ISC 2016.

2.4.3 Tri-generation

Tri-generation (producing locally electricity, heat and cooling) can, depending on the local context, allow for a better deal with the utility in terms of electricity price, while providing “for free” heat (for building) and cooling (for IT equipment).

2.5 Reduce power consumption by dynamic tuning of hardware parameters

Adapting the power consumption of the IT system to the workload can save a substantial amount of energy. Starting with Sandy Bridge, Intel implemented more aggressive power management methods, also called Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS). Some of the controls were exposed to the user allowing, for example, the setting of the maximal frequency for a processor.

This opened a new field of energy efficiency research leading to a better energy efficiency of HPC systems. There are different optimisation spaces related to runtime (how long an application runs – also called Time-to-Solution (TtS)), power consumption (what are peak and average power consumption), and energy consumption (how much energy was consumed when executing an application – also called Energy-to-Solution (EtS)).

The optimisation space exists because the processor frequency has an exponential relationship with power. Figure 8 shows that the application runtime (throughput) doesn’t scale linearly at higher frequencies as the frequency refers to the clock at which the processor cores are operated and the clock of other parts of the system remains constant. So, the application performance at some point saturates. At the same time the power increases exponentially at higher frequencies. This opens the way for EtS optimisation.

One possible technique to use is an Energy-aware job scheduler [9]. Here the applications are profiled in order to find the optimal maximum processor frequency that provides the best EtS. This frequency is automatically set for subsequent runs of this application.

Figure 8: Frequency vs. Power consumption and application runtime

The following figures show analysis results of Energy-aware Scheduling used at the SuperMUC system at LRZ.

Figure 9: LRZ SuperMUC Phase1 application EtS average

Independent of EtS the highest frequency produces the shortest runtime (lowest TtS). Therefore, even though lower frequencies (like 1.2GHz) have the same EtS than higher frequencies (2.5 GHz) the higher frequency makes more sense since more applications can be run on the system in a given timeframe (see Figure 9).

At LRZ the combination of optimal EtS and optimal runtime frequencies was used to define a reasonable default frequency balancing the need for low TtS and best EtS. Figure 10 shows an analysis of normalized EtS of different applications compared to the 2.3 GHz default frequency used at LRZ for the Energy Aware Scheduling.

Figure 10: Comparing EtS from different applications to 2.3GHz default frequency

Even though there are better frequencies for minimizing EtS for different applications, 2.3 GHz represents a good compromise for the application mix at LRZ.

One can increase the complexity of the optimisation space by another dimension if one considers the number of cores/nodes used [10]. Figure 11 shows a 3D surface plot for the Hydro application benchmark looking at EtS, number of nodes, and max CPU frequency. As can be seen one can find different EtS minima's depending on node count and max CPU frequency. This is another area where optimisation potential is currently not fully explored.

Figure 11: Energy optimisation space for Hydro application benchmark

Lastly, besides tuning for energy, power control is becoming more and more important in light of exascale. Figure 12 shows the power distribution of a compute node of CoolMUC2 for different frequencies. Firestarter was used to ensure maximum power consumption thus the shown data shows the maximum. Current CPU technology is very good at saving CPU power when idling. Here the rest of the board components consume as much as CPU and memory in total. With higher frequency, the CPU power consumption starts to dominate the node power consumption. At 2.2 GHz both CPUs of the node consume close to 75% of the node power. One interesting feature is that the node at 1.2 GHz consumes 50% of the power when compared to 2.2 GHz. This behaviour is interesting for the technique of power shedding where for whatever reason the power consumption of an HPC exascale system needs to be reduced without terminating applications.

Figure 12: Average node power distribution for CoolMUC2 (Intel Xeon E5-2690 v3 ("Haswell")) using Firestarter

2.6 Improvement of system availability

Usually, an improvement of system availability is strictly correlated with the SLA (Service Level Agreement) requirements of the IT infrastructure itself (HPC systems, data infrastructure and network connections) and the supporting infrastructure of the data centre.

2.6.1 High availability

High availability is a characteristic of a system, which aims to ensure an agreed level of operational performance, usually uptime, for a higher than normal period.

The strategic purpose of this report is to analyse the circumstances and elements that contribute to the decrease of OpEx and CapEx values. Measures to achieve this goal comprise:

- Improving system availability by reducing mean-time-to-repair based on refined monitoring for fast fault

localization and fault prediction combined with preventive hardware replacement will contribute to increasing the return on investment.

- Intelligent analysis of components which may cause problems in the future, e.g. trend analysis, capacity management, simulations of HPC systems behaviour and its influence on the stability of the data.
- Reduction of personnel due to automation of administrative processes.

Higher availability of the service, in our case HPC service or data access service may require additional investment and/or maintenance costs [11]:

- Bigger amount of hardware which is necessary to achieve the required reliability (IT equipment, electricity, cooling, other DC infrastructure)
- Monitoring and control platforms for PC clusters, software and supporting infrastructure (e.g. Building Management System)

While being in itself an additional investment, a Data Centre Information Management (DCIM) system helps in managing a complex infrastructure and increasing availability:

- **Asset management**
Most popular DCIM solutions have the ability to catalogue IT assets such as network equipment, servers, etc., which are installed in rack cabinets in the data centre. Also, there are some packages that map all connections between devices and from where a particular device is supplied with electricity.
- **Capacity management**
Most of DCIM software available on the market is able to inform the user if there is enough space, available network ports or electric sockets in rack cabinets for new equipment. Furthermore, some DCIM software can detect that equipment is too heavy for a particular rack cabinet, or that the power supply or the cooling system reached its limits and new equipment cannot be added.
- **Real-time monitoring**
Complex DCIM applications gather data and inform if equipment parameters exceed thresholds so that administrators can react to the situation immediately.
- **Trends & reporting**
DCIM systems that monitor equipment parameters in real time are often able to save that data to visualize changes of parameters in the form of graphs or reports.
- **Data centre floor visualization**
In most cases, DCIM systems provide 2D or 3D visualization of server rooms. Some solutions are even able to calculate heat dissipation and display it as a thermal-vision view of the server room.
- **Simulations**
Most complex DCIM solutions have functions to calculate “what if” scenarios, such as a power failure, a cooling system malfunction or the deployment of new equipment, to better understand consequences of such events and take appropriate actions.
- **Workflow**
Some DCIM software implements ticket systems to help automate and document change requests for assets in a data centre. Thus, only qualified personnel are responsible for performing changes to IT assets.
- **Remote control**
Parts of DCIM solutions allow storing login credentials in an encrypted database to help administrators cope with a huge number of IT assets which require remote control.

There are three principles of systems design which can help achieve high availability [12]:

1. Elimination of single points of failure. This means adding redundancy to the system so that failure of a component does not mean failure of the entire system.
2. Reliable crossover. In redundant systems, the crossover point itself tends to become a single point of failure. Reliable systems must provide for reliable crossover.
3. Detection of failures as they occur. If the two principles above are observed, then a user may never see a failure but the maintenance activity must provide the information that an event of fault has happened.

2.6.2 Remove single point of failures

Data centre infrastructure redundancies include cooling and power, but must also have a reliable power distribution path. Essentially, an outage at the facility level should not cause IT systems to be unavailable beyond their defined recovery or availability requirements.

The data centre availability is usually rated by tiers which were originally developed by The Uptime Institute [14]. Attributes such as Basic (Tier 1), Redundant capacity components (Tier 2), concurrently maintainable (Tier 3) and Fault tolerant (Tier 4), are used to describe the availability of site infrastructures. The Tier 1 certified facility will include components starting from the emergency power generator and UPS and guarantees a basic level of availability. A facility that does not benefit from a power generator will not achieve any tier rating.

Building a redundant data centre is always a challenge for smaller organizations that have high availability requirements for their IT systems, but do not have the budget to implement a highly redundant or fault-tolerant facility. This is where options like hosting or collocation become appealing to smaller organizations. The cost for access to a hardened facility is shared by many users and becomes an operational cost rather than a large capital expenditure. Both options may significantly decrease the OpEx parameter of the institution without any investments (CapEx) necessary. There are several examples when companies but also R&D institutions decide to go that way, e.g. CERN (outsourced HTC clusters) or Eurofusion (HPC system located in Italy, 2016) [15], [16].

IT and data centre/storage managers working in high-risk areas for natural disasters should never forget that even the most redundant data centre is still a single point of failure by itself.

Ultimately, it is the recovery and availability requirements of the IT infrastructure supporting the business activity that dictates the availability requirements of the data centre facility. The higher the impact of an outage on business, the easier it becomes to justify the cost of redundancy. This is very similar to disaster recovery.

Figure 13: The disaster recovery expenditure and costs of unavailability

When planning for disaster recovery, a lot of effort is put into ensuring that the critical components of the IT infrastructure have the necessary redundancies in place to support the availability or recovery functionality required by the end users, i.e. scientists or business [13].

2.6.3 Hidden costs of applications service unavailability

When an IT service, application or system goes down, it can be quite easy to calculate the cost in terms of lost productivity, IT support, and the effects on SLA (service level agreement). It is obvious that the site effect of unavailability will increase the cost of maintaining the system or the ratio results vs. costs (higher cost of achieving the same result because of timely closed services). In addition we can observe hidden costs that do not show up on the balance sheet. Most of us do not even think about those because they do not have a “real” line-item

number associated with them, but they can actually be far more costly than the figures associated with system failures.

One of the major negative effects of technology problems is loyalty. These do not show up in annual reports, but repeated failures can erode confidence in a technology company’s brand. This aspect is fully understandable in the business world, but is also affecting R&D data centres, where users expect fully operational facilities without unexpected downtime. And while this is a “soft cost,” decreased loyalty can have a negative effect on DC visibility over time as disappointed users tend to move to other centres that are perceived as more reliable.

There are many other hidden costs associated with technology outages, including the human cost of troubleshooting, dealing with the backlash of determining root causes of system outages, and designing ways to eliminate problems.

2.7 Trade-off considerations

- System density

A smaller floor footprint saves space in the machine hall and enables shorter distribution paths thus saving costs of power and IT network cabling. The increasing signal rate allows only for relatively short cable lengths, so there is a need for dense packing.

On the other hand, increasing power densities within racks raise the need to move to liquid cooling. This requires specialized mechanical and electrical cooling systems and produces a higher load per m² which necessitates a larger investment in floor statics and structural analysis of the building.

- Cooling options

While some parts like CPUs, especially in very dense installations, benefit from or even require direct liquid cooling, other parts of the system, e.g. memory or power supplies, may not be prepared for liquid cooling. Here, air cooling can be used for the heat that does not go into the liquid. Appropriate environmental conditions in the machine hall will allow for accommodating a wide range of vendor technology.

Pros and cons of waste heat re-use or making it available to a third party for use now or in future have to be weighed up. Does the expected gain in operating costs justify the expense for the investment? Does it require the use of specific temperature ranges for the cooling? This would impact other design choices as well as future hardware choices.

Moreover, there is a trade-off between the savings of higher coolant temperatures vs. the impact this may have on the compute performance and the stability of the system.

- Infrastructure power

The total lifetime costs, in particular power consumption cost, have to be considered when regarding the trade-off in terms of investment in advanced cooling and electrical supply systems (e.g. combined heating and cooling) versus ongoing running costs. The savings of investing in electricity load management to avoid periods of peak demand should be evaluated. It is important to meter the degree of efficiency of the UPS system and assess the trade-off between investment and operational costs as well as to weigh up where UPS redundancy is necessary.

- System utilisation (availability and usability)

Investing in a Data Centre Information Management (DCIM) system should be considered. The ability to monitor and measure will not only help with preventative maintenance but also allows to accurately measure TCO and energy efficiency.

3. Survey on state of the art costs and best practices in cost reduction

The PRACE Research Infrastructure provides access to HPC systems which are among the most powerful in the world to best meet the needs of the European HPC user community. Within work package “HPC Commissioning and Prototyping” (WP5) current and upcoming system architectures and technologies towards exascale and the requirements of the users are investigated and a subtask focuses on best practices for energy-efficient HPC centre infrastructure design and operations.

A WP5-wide poll related to the TCO cost breakdown of HPC systems in PRACE data centres has been conducted to find the most relevant cost factors which must be considered when purchasing, installing or upgrading, and operating an HPC system. Another goal of the survey was the compilation of the most promising strategies for cost reduction without decreasing the value of the investment. Eleven sites responded to the request but not all questions have been answered by every partner. Table 1 gives an overview of the spectrum of data centres.

	min	max	average	median
Machine hall floor space	98 m ²	3160 m ²	1158 m ²	1000 m ²
Total power available	0.35 MW	10 MW	3.8 MW	2.1 MW
Power purchase price	72 €/MWh	160 €/MWh	105 €/MWh	93 €/MWh
PUE	1.2	1.8	1.36	1.3

Table 1: Key parameters of data centre infrastructure

The range of the installed supercomputer capacity is summarised in Table 2.

	min	max	average	median
Floor space	8 m ²	682 m ²	212 m ²	90 m ²
Power consumption	0.2 MW	4.6 MW	2.4 MW	2.5 MW
System capability (Rpeak)	0.4 PFlop/s	11.1 PFlop/s	3.4 PFlop/s	1.8 PFlop/s

Table 2: Key parameters of the supercomputer

Hybrid cooling is the most commonly used cooling option for the systems under consideration. In most cases a water-cooled rear door is attached to the racks but there is also a more integrated vendor-specific solution. While some smaller systems are operated with full air cooling, direct liquid cooling is required for larges systems where up to 90 % of the heat is removed by water.

The survey asked for a TCO cost breakdown of the most recently installed HPC system at the data centre.

The full text of the cost categories regarded in this questionnaire is listed in appendix A.

Figure 14: TCO breakdown

Category	min	max	average	median
IT equipment CapEx	27.0 %	70.0 %	46.8 %	44.2 %
Building and Technical facility CapEx	2.0 %	50.0 %	14.4 %	6.5 %
IT system maintenance OpEx	0.7 %	18.0 %	6.7 %	5.5 %
Building and Technical facility OpEx	1.0 %	11.0 %	5.2 %	5.0 %
Electricity costs OpEx	6.5 %	22.0 %	14.2 %	14.0 %
Staff OpEx	1.0 %	27.0 %	11.1 %	10.5 %
Other	0.5 %	4.6 %	1.7 %	1.3 %

Table 3: TCO cost breakdown

The TCO fraction of electricity costs is strongly affected by the differing electricity prices in the EU member states [17].

Moreover, the survey asked for an assessment of the current efforts on cost saving strategies at the data centre.

The full text of the characterisation of saving strategies regarded in this questionnaire is listed in appendix B.

Figure 15: Invested efforts in saving strategies

Category	current min	current max	current average	future min	future max	future average
System density	1	10	5.7	1	10	5.8
Sustainability	3	10	5.4	3	10	6.2
Right-sizing	3	10	6.2	5	10	7.1
Cooling	7	10	8.7	8	10	9.1
Infrastructure power						
Load management	1	5	2.4	1	10	3.9
Infrastructure power						
UPS efficiency	3	10	6.1	1	10	5.7
Infrastructure power						
Level of redundancy	1	10	6.4	1	10	6.6
Infrastructure power						
Diminution of losses	1	8	4.6	1	10	5.6
Reduce system power						
Tuning CPU frequency	1	10	4.2	1	10	6.0
Reduce system power						
Energy-aware scheduler	1	10	3.6	1	10	5.7
Reduce system power						
Unused resources	2	8	5.0	2	9	5.6
Reduce system power						
Virtualisation/consolidation	1	7	2.2	1	8	3.1
System availability						
Monitoring	3	10	7.1	6	10	7.6
System availability						
Fault prediction	1	10	4.1	3	10	5.5

Table 4: Efforts on cost saving strategies (averages of given marks 1-10)

Plans for the future regarding efforts on cost saving strategies have been considered as well. The general trend is a higher sensitivity to cost saving measures and significant increase can be observed in the fields of power right-sizing and reduction of system power by CPU frequency tuning and energy-aware scheduling.

4. TCO based procurement of supercomputers

4.1 Cost evaluation of a custom workload as TCO basis

The method presented here gives an example of an approach to use TCO-based criteria for procurement.

Finding the best value for the investment and the cost of operations (CapEx and OpEx) involved during the lifetime of a supercomputer is an obvious objective. Therefore it is relevant to define a workload as close as possible to the expected exploitation of the machine. The metrics from this workload (Time-to-Solution, TtS and Energy-to-Solution, EtS) can be used to evaluate the actual service produced by the facility during its lifetime (i.e. how many times can the standard workload be run on the machine). The result of the evaluation can help to make a decision based on the best efficiency of the purchased facility related to the usage.

The methodology relies on a custom workload to calculate the TCO for a given period of time. The outcome is aimed at making a good decision for a system selection. It will not compare architecture in a « Cartesian » way (best interconnect, best memory BW, best collective messages passing, best I/O subsystem or whatever characteristic), the approach targets "best value for money". The preliminary work is to define a workload that represents the production on the machine that will be purchased.

The workload is a set of codes to be run simultaneously on the whole machine with an exclusive allocation of nodes, representing a typical exploitation. Then, based on the measurement of the global energy envelope and the wall-clock time of the representative workload, the impact during the lifetime of the machine of the global energy and the total number of time the workload can be run is calculated.

As the OpEx is part of the TCO, and considering the growth of energy cost proportion within OpEx and with respect to CapEx, a strong incentive is addressed to the provider to propose an energy efficient technology and associated monitoring tools.

Method

The calculation of the total cost of ownership (TCO) includes the following cost elements:

- Machine acquisition
- Maintenance over 5 years (expected life time of the system)
- Infrastructure specific add-ons
- Complementary staff required for 5 years exploitation
- Energy cost over 5 years

Variable definitions:

t : wall-clock time of the workload

E_{Ct} : Energy consumption by computational nodes

E_{Dt} : Energy consumption from disks and service nodes

E_{Ut} : Energy consumption from internal cooling devices

c : total core count of the proposed configuration

c_{wl} : core count used for the selected workload

T : Number of second in 5 years

N : Number of runs of the workload during 5 years

E_T : Total energy consumption during 5 years

E_C : Energy of computational part during 5 years

E_D : Energy of storage and service nodes during 5 years

E_U : Energy of internal cooling device during 5 years

TCO_E : TCO due to energy consumption during 5 years

PUE_{air} : Power Usage Effectiveness for air cooled devices

PUE_{coldw} : Power Usage Effectiveness for "Cold water" cooled devices

PUE_{hotw} : Power Usage Effectiveness for "Hot water" cooled devices

Energy calculations:

$$E_C = E_{Ct} * \frac{c}{c_{wl}} * PUE_{compute} * \frac{T}{t}$$
$$E_D = E_{Dt} * PUE_{disk} * \frac{T}{t}$$
$$E_U = E_{Ut} * PUE_{cdu} * \frac{T}{t}$$

With

$$PUE_{compute} = 1 + [(PUE_{air} - 1) * \%_{air-for-compute}] + [(PUE_{coldw} - 1) * \%_{coldw-for-compute}] + [(PUE_{hotw} - 1) * \%_{hotw-for-compute}]$$

$$PUE_{disk} = 1 + [(PUE_{air} - 1) * \%_{air-for-disk}] + [(PUE_{coldw} - 1) * \%_{coldw-for-disk}] + [(PUE_{hotw} - 1) * \%_{hotw-for-disk}]$$

$$PUE_{cdu} = 1 + [(PUE_{air} - 1) * \%_{air-cdu}] + [(PUE_{coldw} - 1) * \%_{coldw-for-cdu}] + [(PUE_{hotw} - 1) * \%_{hotw-for-cdu}]$$

Then:

$$E_T = E_C + E_D + E_U$$

$$E_T = \left[(E_{Ct} * \frac{c}{c_{wl}} * PUE_{compute}) + (E_{Dt} * PUE_{disk}) + (E_{Ut} * PUE_{cdu}) \right] * \frac{T}{t}$$

$$TCO_E = E_T * EnergyCost$$

$$TCO = Purchase + Maintenance + Infrastructure + Staff + TCO_E$$

Where:

- *Purchase* is the acquisition cost of the machine
- *Maintenance* is the maintenance cost over 5 years
- *Infrastructure* is the specific cost of infrastructure for the machine
- *Staff* is the cost for complementary staff for machine exploitation over 5 years

Cost of the workload (TCO_b) takes into account the number of time (N) it will be possible to run it over 5 years

$$N = \frac{c}{c_{wl}} * \frac{T}{t}$$

$$TCO_b = TCO / N$$

4.2 Procurement decision using cost workload

The entire procurement process usually takes into account a series of criteria such as:

- site integration
- compliance with required features and standards
- expandability
- reliability commitments
- performance results

Each of it associated with a specific weight leading to a global ranking as a basis for decision-making.

The global TCO, as exposed in the previous subsection, is an additional criterion which might be used instead of (application) performance results unless Time-to-Solution is a business critical objective which would overrule any cost considerations. As a matter of fact, the formulas TCO_b and TCO reflect the best value for money one can expect from a given budget and are in particular adequate to the acquisition of HPC systems intended to run scientific simulations at scale.

GENCI has used TCO criteria in its three last acquisition processes and in the final evaluation for the ranking of all tenders TCO was weighted as 40%.

5. Summary and conclusions

An important result of this report is the classification of the most relevant cost categories for a TCO analysis for supercomputers. On the basis of a survey which has been conducted in August 2017 at 11 European HPC centres, information has been collected about each category's share of the costs. As a result of this survey, on average the capital expenditure for IT equipment represents less than half of the total costs (46.8 %). A similar fraction of costs (40.5 %) is due to the investment incurred in developing the infrastructure and the operational and electricity costs collectively. A share of 11.1 % of the TCO is attributed to personnel costs.

The electricity price differs largely among the European countries participating in the survey and varies in the range from 72 € to 160 € per MWh thus leading to analogously varying shares in TCO.

A number of successfully implemented examples for saving infrastructural and operational costs have been regarded in this report. As it seems, the partners have individual preferences. The survey illustrated that a lot of cost saving efforts are made with different intensity at the participating HPC centres. Strategies that are pursued with the highest intensity at one centre appear less interesting at another site, likely because of the local context. Regarding all data centres, on average, investigation of different cooling options seems to be the most promising way to cut down operational costs. Then, improving system availability by monitoring for fast fault localisation is the second highest ranked strategy. As to the survey, nearly all listed cost saving activities are supposed to be intensified in the future.

Moreover, a TCO-assisted method is introduced for supercomputer procurement which may support good decisions both related to the user requirements and also with respect to the local infrastructure.

In relation to the main topic of this white paper, TCO costs related to the infrastructure of the HPC centres, the annually organised European Workshop on HPC Centre Infrastructure is an adequate place for sharing best practices for reducing TCO. This report provides a first overview of the TCO of supercomputers at European HPC centres and ongoing cost cutting activities. A re-evaluation should be done on a regular basis.

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7. Appendix

A. Cost categories

Please give a cost overview related to the main cost factors listed below. We ask here for a percentage value for each of the main cost categories which would give, when summed up, 100% of the total costs.

Investment cost	%
1. IT equipment costs Supercomputer (including system setup and disposal costs) Related it equipment (including installation): storage system, computer centre network Evolution and upgrades within the years of operation	
2. Building and technical facility (new building or adaptation of existing building) Building (floor space for IT equipment and technical facilities, static load requirements) Technical facilities for power supply (e.g. transformers, UPS, distribution) Technical facilities for cooling (e.g. pipes, pumps, chillers, heat exchangers) Investment in security and monitoring (e.g. fire protection, leakage detection, resource consumption measurement)	
Operational costs	%
3. IT system maintenance costs (including vendor support) Maintenance of supercomputer and related IT equipment, system environment related software updates and licenses	
4. Building and technical facility Maintenance of building and technical facilities Maintenance of security and monitoring (e.g. fire protection, leakage detection, resource consumption measurement)	
5. Electricity costs Operational costs for system power and cooling (including non-deductible taxes)	
6. Staff (related to the considered supercomputer) Staff in charge of computer centre operation, system administration/maintenance, user management Training of users and administrators on a regular basis Staff responsible for application support (code profiling, optimisation, porting and scaling, job submission tools) Staff in charge of the building and technical facility	
Additional investment and operational costs	%
7. Other costs Initial application porting (supplemental software costs, user training, application porting) Procurement costs (system selection, determine user/infrastructure requirements, call for tenders, ordering) Application software updates and licenses Management/administration(Insurance, financing costs in case of leasing, inventorying)	

B. Efforts put into cost saving strategies

Mark the intensity of your efforts concerning the respective cost saving strategies in current operation on a scale 1-10 (1=lowest intensity, 10=highest intensity)

X = Current situation

O = Plans for the future (if different from current situation)

Cost saving operation \ Importance	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Compare different systems in terms of density (space footprint, power load etc.)										
2. Build sustainable infrastructure (modular components ready for re-use at follow-up installations)										
3. Right-size power and cooling infrastructure to their precise										

energy requirements										
4. Consider different cooling options , taking full air cooling as reference point, analysing potential cost benefits										
5. Optimise infrastructure power costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.a Electricity load management to avoid periods of peak demand										
5.b UPS power efficiency										
5.c Optimise the level of redundancy for HPC										
5.d Reduce losses in power distribution										
6. Reduce power consumption by dynamic tuning of hardware parameters	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.a Job-dependent tuning of processor frequency settings										
6.b Energy-aware scheduler										
6.c Improved management of unused resources										
6.d Improved utilization by virtual servers / consolidation of servers										
7. Strategies for improving system availability by reducing mean-time-to-repair:	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.a Monitoring for fast fault localization										
7.b Fault prediction combined with preventive hardware replacement										

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